

3D Modeling and Coupled Electromagnetic-Thermal-Fluid Analysis of a Novel Inductive Power Transformer Submerged in Biodegradable Dielectric Fluid

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ABSTRACT

Solid State Transformers (SSTs) are an emerging technology for upgrading and enhancing the distribution and transmission networks. They enable the development of highly controllable and robust smart grids integrating Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and connections for both Alternating Current (AC) and Direct Current (DC) components/lines in Medium Voltage (MV) or Low Voltage (LV) levels. This research paper presents an innovative SST that embeds the state-of-the-art architecture of an Inductive Power Transformer (IPT), under development in the context of SSTAR, a Horizon 2020 project. The IPT is submerged into a biobased, biodegradable dielectric fluid providing the appropriate cooling and insulation characteristics. The analysis presented proposes a 3D coupled electromagnetic-thermal-fluid model to calculate the important aspects of the SST, utilizing the commercial software ANSYS. The results highlight the efficiency and robustness of the proposed architecture, paving the way towards active and environmental-friendly electrical networks.

KEYWORDS

solid state transformer, biodegradable dielectric fluid, forced liquid cooling system, computational fluid dynamics, smart grid.

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INTRODUCTION

The ongoing energy transition has affected the architecture of electrical networks. Distribution and transmission networks are now being populated with Renewable Energy Sources (RES), storage systems, and other distributed resources, aiming to enhance their sustainability and efficiency. [1]. Therefore, the concept of unidirectional, fossil-fuel based, passive networks has become outdated and is being progressively replaced by controllable, active, and bidirectional smart grids [2]. This necessitates a fundamental overhaul of existing infrastructures, including the adoption of advanced configurations such as hybrid AC/DC, more efficient converters, and innovative transformers [3].

Conventional high-power transformers are widely acknowledged to not be fully prepared to overcome the modern-day challenges posed by the electrical grid [4]. These challenges include difficulties in maintaining a constant voltage level in the face of voltage drop over distance and different loads, as well as in controlling the power flow when integrating renewable energy sources [5]. A promising solution to overcome these challenges is the Solid-state Transformer (SST), which has emerged as a ground-breaking technology capable of expanding the traditional functionalities of conventional transformers [6,7]. The SST is a power electronics device that facilitates the efficient connection of separate electrical networks with differing voltage ranges, including medium and low voltage, as well as AC and DC voltage types and even differing frequencies [8]. As such, the SST holds enormous potential for application in the high-power, medium-frequency range [9], offering maximum power density and efficiency within a compact size [10]. The main concept of an SST is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Main concept of an SST connecting power supply and demand

However, SST technology has not yet been sufficiently established worldwide for commercial use [11]. Compared to the conventional transformer, SST technology might result in more controllable, scalable and modular assemblies but on the other hand is more expensive, complex and its design aspects are yet not finalized [12]. Only a few prototypes of up to 15 kV, in the range of 40 kHz, have been developed so far [8]. A critical step towards the facilitation of the SST technology widespread is the optimisation of both the electromagnetic and thermal aspects in a sustainable and cost-efficient way.

Modeling of the electromagnetic and thermal aspects of SSTs

The thermal design of power transformers is a crucial factor that influences their operational lifetime, reliability, and loading capacity [13]. Most transformers operate in immersed liquid conditions thus the excessive heat produced by the electromagnetic losses is the primary cause of insulation performance deterioration. This can be counterbalanced by embodying cooling systems in the transformer. The optimal design of the cooling system is essential to avoid

operating faults and materials degradation due to thermal damage [14] and to achieve a high-power density [15]. The evaluation of hot spot temperatures in the components of the SSTs poses another significant challenge concerning their thermal aspects [16]. The prediction of the hot-spot temperature rise in the structural parts of transformers relies heavily on the distribution of electromagnetic losses. Given that the location of maximum loss density is typically where the hot spot is located, an accurate description of the stray loss distribution is essential to compute the hot-spot temperature rise [17]. Therefore, accurate modeling of liquid flow and temperature distributions within structural components is of utmost importance.

Liquid-immersed power transformers are the dominant type of transformer in power networks, where the dielectric liquid is utilized as both a coolant and insulator [17]. In the case of Solid-state Transformers (SSTs), the temperature regulation of the dielectric fluid is a crucial factor in the design process, as it contributes to voltage insulation enhancement, thereby increasing the SSTs' flexibility and their integration into high-voltage grids. The cooling systems of the electronics can be categorized into natural [18] and forced [19]. The passive cooling systems utilize capillary or gravitational force to circulate the working fluid, while the forced cooling systems are usually driven by a pump, which could offer a significant advantage in terms of thermal removal capability [20]. The design of an efficient cooling system demands meeting the required temperature limits, whilst simultaneously reducing the size, complexity, and overall cost. The most efficient way of cooling of high-power transformers is to make use of forced liquid cooling [21]. This method takes advantage of a liquid's higher heat density, capacity and thermal conductivity compared to air and enables the cooling of concentrated heat sources in remote locations. Therefore, the physical design of the power electronics system is facilitated by enabling the development of more compact systems with higher power density.

Brief literature review

The approximation of thermal distribution in power transformers necessitates the utilization of numerical methods [22]. The electromagnetic and thermal requirements of transformers can be usually assessed using established software packages and appropriate fluid dynamics and thermal models. To achieve this, a magnetic-thermal coupling approach is mostly adopted [23]. Specifically, the stray loss distribution obtained from the electromagnetic analysis serves as the boundary conditions for the thermal analysis. In recent years, numerous studies have been conducted to design and optimize SSTs in order to meet the increasing demand for efficient and sustainable energy systems. A brief literature review is presented below. Beheshtaein et al. [10] developed a hybrid liquid/air cooling system for an SST operating at 13 kV to 7.2 kV, 667 kW, 20 kHz, in order to enhance its efficiency. For this purpose, the part of the forced air-cooling and water-cooling system is modelled in ANSYS MAXWELL/Simplorer, ANSYS-ICEPAK, and ANSYS-FLUENT, respectively. Jia et al. [17] investigated the temperature rise and the mechanical properties of windings in an oil-immersed transformer and Stebel et al. [22] proposed an advanced electromagnetic and thermo-fluid model of disk-type transformer and assessed its thermal characteristics using FEA. Mogorovic et al. [24] developed an algorithm for the design of SSTs, including calculation of losses, magnetic energy and hot-spot temperatures. According to the algorithm, a 100 kW, 10 kHz prototype was developed and tested, verifying the theoretical design. Also, Roger et al. [25] presented a theoretical and experimental investigation on SSTs that incorporate Grain Oriented Electrical Steel (GOES) and the possibility to design SSTs of several MW at a reasonable cost, with a limited number of cells. The authors study the core losses, the eddy currents and their effects on the temperatures developed in the SST. However, all of the aforementioned designs refer to SSTs where the primary and secondary windings are connected, whereas more recent research

focuses on Inductive Power Transformers (IPT) which have a wider application field [26]. In this sense, in [27] the performance of an IPT for wireless charging is studied. For this purpose, a simulation model is developed that combines an electrical circuit with a nonlinear finite element model. Su et al. [28] presented a methodology to design SSTs, focusing mostly on their power electronics. The methodology is evaluated by manufacturing and testing an IPT with operating frequency equal to 200 kHz. Haque et al. [29] compared the performance of a 50 kW IPT considering operation at 22 kHz and 85 kHz, with Si and SiC MOSFET. The system and its components are optimally designed for the two target frequencies and consequent losses are evaluated analytically, through finite element, and circuit analysis. Tian et al. [30] proposed a coupled, semi-numerical model for the thermal analysis of a medium frequency transformer.

Scope of the paper

The purpose of this paper is to present the 3D modeling and the coupled electromagnetic-thermal-fluid analysis of an SST incorporating an IPT, which is under development in the Horizon 2020 SSTAR project [31]. The prototype to be manufactured is designed to operate at 1.5 kV / 0.4 kV with power equal to 50 kW and frequency equal to 50 kHz. The aim is to combine a number of such SSTs in order to reach higher voltage levels in an efficient, safe and sustainable way. For this purpose, the performance of the SST is enhanced through a biobased, biodegradable dielectric fluid which is used not only for insulation but also for forced cooling. The analysis is performed using a 3D coupled electromagnetic-thermal-fluid model to calculate the important aspects of the SST, with the commercial software ANSYS, showcasing the efficiency and robustness of the proposed architecture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section describes the modeling of the SST geometry and the configuration of the cooling system. The governing equations and the boundary conditions are derived and the coupling scheme is presented and discussed.

Geometry of the SST

As at the current point of the ongoing SSTAR project the conceptual design of the SST has been concluded, a simplified geometry will be used for the conduction of the simulations. The geometry of the model consists of the dielectric fluid, the magnetic core, the aluminum shield and the Litz windings, submerged in the dielectric fluid. The fluid volume also contains the inlet and outlet ports which allow the circulation of the cooling liquid.

Windings are composed of round copper Litz wires of in a typical bundle-type configuration [32]. Since a Litz wire bundle can contain hundreds or even thousands of small strands, it would be computationally insufficient to model and analyse every strand explicitly using finite element analysis (FEA). Therefore, a Litz bundle is modelled as a single homogenized object with the same outer diameter. This significantly reduces the number of finite elements and design unknowns, vastly improving simulation efficiency [33,34]. The homogenized modeling approach of a Litz wire is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Proposed Homogenized Litz Wires Model

Figure 3 illustrates the model's geometry, while Figure 4 depicts the primary geometrical dimensions of the SST.

Figure 3. Simplified geometry of the SST. Left: isometric view, Middle: Isometric view with top-plane section, Right: Isometric view with right-plane section

Figure 4. Main geometric dimensions of the SST

The configuration of the cooling system is illustrated in Figure 5-left. A single-phase dielectric ester fluid is used as the cooling medium. The inductive power transfer is submerged in an aluminium tank filled with the liquid. Warm oil at low pressure exits the tank and enters the mini coolant pump that delivers the liquid to the mini channels heat exchanger (MCHE). MCHE removes the heat from the oil to the ambient temperature of the environment. The thermal balance of the microchannel heat exchanger is shown in Figure 4-right. The ester oil flows with a mass flow rate of 0.5 kg/s entering the exchanger at a temperature of 80 °C, which is the temperature of the fluid in the outlet of the tank. The fluid temperature leaving the radiator is calculated at 60°C. The assigned ambient temperature is 20 °C, and the airflow velocity is 10 m/s.

Figure 5. Cooling system configuration (left) and thermal balance of the heat exchanger (right)

Modeling approach, governing equations and coupling scheme

The modeling approach is based on the interaction and transfer of data between two main models: the electromagnetic-thermal model and the thermal-fluid model. The stray losses of the electromagnetic model are calculated to obtain the heat source which is used by the thermal sub-model according to [35]. In the magnetic field analysis, the T- Ω method [36] is used to compute the stray losses of the transformer.

The equations governing the 3-D coupled electromagnetic-thermal-fluid analysis are described below. Using the Maxwell's equations and based on the Coulomb gauge, the energy equation in the eddy current region is used, according to [37]. Similarly, the energy equation in the non-eddy current regions which includes the magnetic core, the non-conductive parts and the current source regions can be formulated [37]. The stray losses in the metallic parts of the transformer include eddy current losses and hysteresis losses.

In the thermal-fluid coupling analysis, the flow is modelled using the mass, momentum and energy conservation laws. The flow is considered turbulent [22] and is modelled using the k-e model. The heat transfer analysis at the boundaries is conducted using the heat transfer equation leading to the calculation of the internal convection heat transfer coefficient of the transformer. The system of the described equations is solved using ANSYS Maxwell-Icepak software in order to calculate the magnetic, thermal and fluid characteristics. The coupling scheme is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Coupling scheme

Material assignment

Table 1 presents the materials used in the simulations. The temperature-dependent properties are derived from [38].

Table 1. Material properties

MODEL ASSIGNEMENTS		ELECTROMAGNETIC		THERMAL - Fluid	
Solids	Material	Properties	Value / Unit	Properties	Value / Unit
LV Windings & HV Windings	Copper 1650 & Copper 330	Relative Permittivity	1	Thermal Conductivity	400 W/m°C
		Relative Permeability	0.9999		
		Bulk Conductivity	58,000,000 Siemens/m Temp.-depedent ¹	Mass Density	8,933 kg/m ³
		Loss Tangent	0		
		Mass Density	8,933 kg/m ³	Specific Heat	385 J/kg°C
		Composition	Litz Wire		
		Wire Type	Round	Expansion Coefficient	1.77 10 ⁻⁵ 1/°C
		Strand Number	1,650 & 330		
		Wire Diameter	0.16 mm	Material Type	Solid
Primary Core &	Ferrite	Relative Permittivity	12	Thermal Conductivity	4 W/m°C
		Relative Permeability	Non-Linear B-H Curve		

Secondary Core		Bulk Conductivity	0.15 Siemens/m	Mass Density	4,600 kg/m ³
		Loss Tangent	0		
		Core Loss Model	Electrical Steel Based on B-P Experimental Curve	Specific Heat	750 J/kg°C
		Mass Density	4,600 kg/m ³	Expansion Coefficient	10 ⁻⁵ 1/°C
		Composition	Solid	Material Type	Solid
Primary Shield & Secondary Shield	Aluminum	Relative Permittivity	1	Thermal Conductivity	237.5 W/m°C
		Relative Permeability	1.000021		
		Bulk Conductivity	38,000,000 Siemens/m Temp.-depedent ²	Mass Density	2,689 kg/m ³
		Loss Tangent	0	Specific Heat	951 J/kg°C
		Mass Density	2689 kg/m ³	Expansion Coefficient	2.33·10 ⁻⁵ 1/°C
		Composition	Solid	Material Type	Solid
		Relative Permittivity	3	Thermal Conductivity	0.156 W/m°C
Dielectric Fluid	Mineral Oil	Relative Permeability	2.5	Mass Density	920 kg/m ³
		Bulk Conductivity	3 10 ⁻⁷ Siemens/m	Specific Heat	1,940 J/kg°C
		Dielectric Loss tan	0.015	Thermal Expansion Coefficient	0.000675 1/°C
		Magnetic Loss tan	0.001	Thermal Material Type	Fluid
		Mass Density	920 kg/m ³	Thermal Diffusivity	8.74 10 ⁻⁵ m ² /s
		Composition	Solid	Molecular Mass	0.452 kg/mol
				Dynamic Viscosity	0.061 Pa s

¹ if (Temp <=20, 1, 1/(1+0.0039*(Temp-22))) Where 0.0039 Temperature Coefficient of Resistance of Copper

² if (Temp <=20, 1, 1/(1+0.00403*(Temp-22))) Where 0.00403 Temperature Coefficient of Resistance of Aluminum

Excitations and boundary conditions

The eddy current analysis for the electromagnetic model is carried out in Ansys Maxwell by selecting the eddy current solution type, which computes steady-state, time-varying (AC) magnetic fields at a given frequency in the frequency domain. Several assumptions are made; i.e. that all objects are stationary and the source of the static magnetic field is a sinusoidal AC

(peak) in the conductors, while time-varying external magnetic fields are neglected. The quantities solved are the magnetic field (H) and the magnetic scalar potential (Ω), while the density (J) and magnetic flux density (B) can be calculated from (H). The material permeabilities and conductivities are anisotropic but linear. Regarding the eddy current solution, the boundaries at the interface between objects are natural, thus the (H) field is continuous across the boundary, while the outer boundaries are perceived as Neumann conditions.

The cooling system's operation under a specific thermal load has been simulated using Ansys Icepak by specifying a steady-state temperature and flow solution type. The solution type is determined after receiving the power loss results from Ansys Maxwell, assuming that the temperature and flow variables remain constant over time and that the system has reached a steady-state operating condition. Several assumptions were made during the simulation. The system was considered to have reached an equilibrium state and the material properties of the system components were constant. The inlet and outlet temperatures were also specified, and the external surfaces of the inlet and outlet pipes were designated as stationary and conducting walls, respectively, with specific thicknesses and temperatures.

Table 3. Excitations

Assignment	Excitations	Properties	Value / Unit
Primary HV_Windings	Coil Terminal - Stranded	Number of Conductors	20
		Direction	Point Out of Terminal
		Winding Type	Current
		Current	31.25 A
		No of Parallel Branches	1
		Phase	0°
Secondary LV_Windings	Coil Terminal - Stranded	Number of Conductors	5
		Direction	Point Into Terminal
		Winding Type	Current
		Current	118.75 A
		No of Parallel Branches	1
		Phase	45°

Computational mesh

The computational mesh consists of tetrahedral elements. The number of elements was 98136 for the primary core, 98,216 for the secondary core, 255,463 for the primary shield, 253,050 for the secondary shield, 1,584,266 for the dielectric fluid, 127,295 for the high-voltage winding and 129,595 for the low voltage winding.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of the simulation. The results presented are the core, ohmic and dielectric losses, the temperature distributions and the pressure-velocity fields. The results are presented in the form of contour plots.

Figure 9 presents the power loss density in cores (a), windings (b) and in the dielectric fluid (c). The total core loss in primary and secondary cores is calculated approximately to 0.5 kW. The loss distribution in the cores indicates that the maximum values are located at the windings position. The total power loss in the windings is presented in Figure 9-b and is calculated to be 0.25 kW. As expected, the power loss distribution in the low voltage winding is decreased compared to the power loss in the high voltage winding by at least one order of magnitude. This can be attributed to the reduced mutual inductance between the coils due to the presence of a dielectric gap and the cancellation of the eddy currents produced on the aluminium shield by the magnetic field. Finally, Figure 9-c displays the distribution of the power loss density in the dielectric fluid which is calculated in the order of 0.02 kW.

Figure 9. Power loss density for (a) primary and secondary cores, (b) high and low voltage windings and (c) dielectric fluid

The analysis of the temperature distribution in the structural components of the transformer yields that the structural parts exhibit higher temperatures at locations of higher power loss density. The temperature variation on the component's structure was calculated within the acceptable range of 5°C. These temperature levels indicate that the IPT is operating within desired temperature limits and that the heat transfer mechanisms, including conduction, convection, and radiation, are effectively maintaining a thermal equilibrium state. Figure 10 presents the temperature distribution in the primary and secondary structures. The minimum

temperature achieved was 60°C while the maximum was 64.7°C. It can also be observed that the maximum temperature values in the primary structures of the IPT are higher than those in the secondary structures. This is expected due to the inductive efficiency between the transmitter and receiver, which leads to electromagnetic loss due to the gap, resulting in higher heat generation values in the transmitting primary coil. The maximum temperatures are concentrated in areas where the windings are placed (Figure 11-a,c). The results shows that the maximum temperature of the aluminium plate is mainly concentrated in the areas near the windings (Figure 11-b). Finally, it can be seen that the dielectric fluid temperature increases from the inlet to the outlet, (Figure 10-d) indicating that it absorbs some of the thermal energy produced by the structural components and transports it to the heat exchanger for dissipation. The maximum temperature rise of the fluid in a thermal equilibrium state was 14°C. The temperature rise of the fluid may also be influenced by factors such as the flow rate and heat transfer coefficient of the fluid, as well as the temperature of the heat exchanger.

Figure 10. Temperature distribution in the components of the transformers (a) primary and secondary cores, (b) primary and secondary shield, (c) high and low voltage windings and (d) dielectric fluid

Table 4 shows the comparison between the maximum temperature obtained in this study and the one obtained by Mogorovitc et al. [24] and Beheshtaein et al. [10]. The results of this study agree with the ones obtained by Beheshtaein et al. [10] that also used a forced cooling system. Also, by comparing the results of this study with the results derived in [24] it is verified that the

utilisation of a forced cooling liquid system significantly decreases the temperature levels and it is expected to enhance the efficiency and the robustness of the proposed architecture.

Table 4. Maximum temperature comparison with literature

Literature	Max temperature	Nominal Values	Cooling system	Type
Mogorovic et al. [24]	125 °C	100 kW, 10 kHz	Natural convective air cooling	Shell
Beheshtaein et al. [10]	64 °C	667 kW, 20 kHz	Hybrid, forced air and water	Shell
This paper	64.7 °C	50 kW, 50 kHz	Forced liquid cooling with biobased dielectric fluid	IPT

Finally, the pressure and velocity characteristics of the flow are presented in Figure 11. It can be observed that the structural elements of the transformer (such as the primary shield and windings) may guide or redirect the flow of the dielectric fluid, leading to the development of positive and negative (smaller than the atmospheric) pressure (Figure 11-a) which is followed by the development of flow circulation zones close to the transformer's parts (Figure 11-b). The presence of these pressure changes and the resulting flow of the fluid may affect the overall heat transfer characteristics of the transformer, as well as the pressure and energy balances within the system.

Figure 11. Flow characteristics of the dielectric fluid. a) pressure contours, b) velocity contours and vector field

CONCLUSION

In this study steady-state one-way electromagnetic-thermal-fluid coupling scheme was developed using ANSYS in order to simulate the magnetic, thermal and flow characteristics of a novel inductive power transformer submerged in biodegradable dielectric fluid. A forced cooling scheme was developed and utilised in order to decrease the developed temperatures resulting from the electromagnetic power losses. The preliminary results indicate that the temperature levels in the components of the transformer remain relatively medium (maximum temperature obtained was 64.7 °C) due to the heat dissipation from the cooling system. The results are found to have an initially good agreement with previously published results from the literature. This highlights the potential of the proposed design to further decrease the developed temperatures and enhance the efficiency and robustness of the proposed architecture, paving the way towards active and environmental-friendly electrical networks. The conduction of

parametric investigations concerning the effect of critical parameters of the cooling system (such as the cooling flow rate, the inflow pressure, the cooling medium etc.) and the experimental verification of the results are programmed as the next steps of this research.

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